

SECTION OF SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC SCIENCES

IMPACT OF MACROECONOMIC CONDITIONS AND MARKET TRENDS ON RESIDENTIAL PROPERTY VALUATION

Yarov Y.

Kyrgyz National University named after Zhusup Balasagyn

Abstract

This article examines the key factors influencing residential property valuation, with a focus on macroeconomic conditions and market trends. It analyzes the impact of inflation, interest rates, income levels, and economic growth on housing affordability and demand. Special attention is given to social and environmental trends, including urbanization, demographic changes, the rise of remote work, and the growing interest in eco-friendly housing. It demonstrates the interrelationship between economic factors and buyer preferences, enabling more accurate predictions of price fluctuations and market development.

Keywords: property valuation, macroeconomics, market trends, inflation, interest rates, housing demand, eco-friendly housing, urbanization, demographics.

Introduction

The valuation of residential property is a complex process that is shaped by a variety of factors. These influences include macroeconomic conditions, demographic changes, and environmental preferences within the population. In the context of economic globalization, housing prices are increasingly determined by the interaction of global and local market dynamics. Various key macroeconomic elements such as inflation or employment levels greatly affect housing affordability and the level of investment in real estate.

Beyond macroeconomic parameters, current market trends also significantly influence the real estate sector. These include the growing popularity of remote work, a preference for eco-friendly housing, and a shift in buyer preferences towards suburban areas. These trends are reshaping the structure of supply and demand, creating new behavioral models in the real estate market. With increasing migration and population growth in cities, housing demand in metropolitan areas continues to rise and leads to higher prices. Some regions may experience population decline, resulting in more stable real estate prices.

Both macroeconomic factors and market trends have a complex and interconnected impact on housing prices. Understanding these interrelations is essential for forecasting future price fluctuations and developing

effective asset management strategies. In an environment of heightened market volatility, it is important to consider shifts in the economy and buyer preferences. The aim of this study is to analyze the influence of macroeconomic conditions and market trends on residential property valuation.

Main part. Analysis of macroeconomic factors

Residential property prices are shaped by macroeconomic conditions that determine overall economic stability, purchasing power, and the sector's attractiveness to investors. These circumstances influence housing supply and demand through income levels, credit accessibility, and general business activity. During periods of economic growth, consumers are more inclined to purchase property, which can drive up prices, while economic downturns tend to restrain market activity.

Macroeconomic factors provide the foundation for stable or volatile price behavior. Central bank policies, shifts in employment structures, and general economic development create conditions for long-term fluctuations in housing values. In recent years, the growth in the residential property market and rising property prices have become important economic indicators. According to 2024 statistics [1], in 2023, the real estate market reached a volume of \$487,8 billion, reflecting the general state of the economy and the appeal of real estate as an investment asset (fig. 1).

Figure 1. Forecast of the global residential property market volume, million dollars

Inflation is one of the key macroeconomic factors affecting the real estate market. Rising **inflation** reduces the purchasing power of the population, often leading to decreased demand for housing. High inflation also raises the costs of construction and property maintenance. This process can lead to an increase in housing prices. This condition can have a dual effect, and it depends on the level and pace of price changes for goods and services in the economy.

Interest rates play a significant role in shaping property values, as most real estate transactions are financed through mortgage lending. High interest rates make mortgages less affordable for the population, thereby reducing housing demand. During periods of

low interest rates, demand for real estate rises, which can lead to higher prices. Central bank policy on interest rate regulation directly influences the dynamics of supply and demand in the housing market.

Employment levels and **household incomes** directly impact citizens' purchasing power and, consequently, demand for residential property. High employment levels and income growth increase housing demand, leading to price rises. During economic downturns, when unemployment rises, demand for real estate decreases, and housing prices may stabilize or even decline. Labor market conditions serve as an important indicator for forecasting price fluctuations in the housing market (table 1).

Table 1.

The impact of employment level on housing affordability and cost [2, 3]

Employment factor	Description of impact	Effect on housing demand and prices
High employment level	Increased employment leads to growth in population income	Increased demand for housing, especially in large cities
Decrease in unemployment	Increased population confidence in income stability	Increased demand for home purchases, price growth
Salary increase	Improved purchasing power	Increased housing prices in economically active regions
Unemployment or unstable employment	Decreased demand for purchasing, increased rental demand	Decrease or stabilization of purchase housing prices

Economic growth strengthens the purchasing power of the population and supports the development of the real estate market. When Gross Domestic Product (GDP) grows, investment in construction and demand for residential property increase, leading to higher property values. During economic downturns, real estate market activity declines, accompanied by a decrease in housing prices. Long-term economic growth creates a stable foundation for rising property prices, while short-term fluctuations may cause temporary changes in demand and prices.

In addition to individual factors, **overall macroeconomic stability** is an essential aspect. In times of economic instability, such as crises or recessions, buyers and investors often adopt a wait-and-see approach, reducing real estate market activity. Macroeconomic instability can lead to sharp fluctuations in housing prices, delays, or even temporary freezes in construction projects.

Macroeconomic factors have a fundamental impact on the residential real estate market, determining the dynamics of supply and demand. Inflation, interest rates, income levels, and economic growth directly affect housing affordability and set general price trends. Understanding these factors allows for a more accurate assessment of market prospects and adaptation to changing economic conditions, which is especially crucial for investors and buyers in an unstable economic environment.

Market trends and their impact on housing prices

The residential real estate market is subject to various market trends that shape its development and price dynamics. These trends include urbanization, changes in demographic composition, the growing popularity of

remote work, and increased demand for environmentally friendly housing. It is essential to understand how each of these trends influences pricing and shapes current market conditions.

Urbanization remains one of the strongest factors driving housing price increases in large cities and metropolitan areas. According to the United Nations [4], approximately 55% of the world's population lives in cities, and this share continues to grow steadily. The influx of people into urban areas leads to increased housing demand. It results in rising prices and reduced housing affordability. In regions experiencing population outflow, on the contrary, demand for real estate declines, which can help stabilize or even reduce prices. Over the past decade, there has been rapid development in suburban and peripheral areas, as many buyers seek to purchase homes outside the city where prices are usually lower [5]. Immigration stimulates the development of new areas, expand the boundaries of cities and contribute to economic growth. It can also lead to increased competition in the market and an increase in the cost of real estate. House prices, depending on the rate of urbanization and immigration levels, are expected to continue to rise between 2010 and 2050 by an average of 4,42% to 18,5% [6].

Demographic trends, such as an aging population and changes in household structure, also significantly impact the real estate market. An increasing proportion of elderly people may reduce demand for large and multi-family homes. While young families and working professionals are often more interested in smaller apartments in central areas. The rise in single-person households also increases demand for smaller apartments, especially in major cities, which can drive up prices in this segment of the market.

With the growing popularity of **remote work**, many people are no longer tied to an office, allowing them to choose their place of residence based on other factors such as environmental quality, infrastructure convenience, and housing affordability. According to a forecast [7], by 2025, approximately 32,6 million Americans, or around 22% of the workforce, are projected to be working remotely. This leads to increased demand for housing in suburban and rural areas, where real estate costs are lower. As a result, demand in central areas has somewhat decreased, contributing to a more balanced distribution of property prices across various geographic zones. In large metropolitan areas, prices remain consistently high due to the appeal of these cities for professional and career growth.

The growing interest in **environmentally sustainable housing** becomes one of the most significant market trends. More and more buyers prefer housing that minimizes environmental impact, using energy-efficient materials, low energy consumption, and renewable energy systems. Environmental quality also plays an important role in housing prices, as areas with a favorable ecology, low pollution levels, and access to green spaces become particularly attractive to buyers. This factor is confirmed by 2024 studies [8], which found that the value of residential units in relatively more polluted areas increased by approximately 2% after environmental regulations were introduced. Other studies have shown that higher proportions of greenery and visual green space contribute to about a 20% higher growth in housing prices [9].

In recent years, real estate has come to be seen not only as housing but also as an **investment asset**, which enhances its market value. The investment appeal of real estate is due to its stability and lower susceptibility to inflation risks compared to other assets. The demand for residential property as an investment tool contributes to price growth, especially in large cities. In addition, there is a significant increase in rental properties, which further boosts real estate prices.

Market trends have a significant impact on housing prices, shaping demand and changing buyer preferences. Urbanization, demographic shifts, the growing interest in eco-friendly housing, and the rise of remote work lead to price increases in desirable areas and greater demand for specific types of properties. These trends emphasize the need for the market to adapt to changing conditions and preferences, which contributes to more balanced and sustainable housing market development.

Conclusion

Residential property prices are shaped by both macroeconomic conditions and current market trends, as it results in a layered and dynamic pricing structure

in this sector. Various macroeconomic factors, such as inflation or economic growth, provide the overall economic foundation. They also determine the purchasing power and housing affordability for the population. Market trends reflect shifts in consumer preferences and social changes, forming demand for specific types of properties. It is important to consider both groups of factors for accurate forecasting and long-term housing price management. This approach allows for effective adaptation to changing conditions and ensures the stability of the real estate market.

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